

Graphene oxide as a nanoadditive in cementitious composites: A comparative study of portland and magnesium oxychloride cement binders

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ABSTRACT

The addition of graphene oxide (GO) to cement-based materials can improve their mechanical performance and durability. However, there are few direct comparisons between different binder systems. While GO has been widely studied in Portland cement (PC), its effect on alternative binders like magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) has usually been explored separately and under different experimental conditions. This study offers a direct comparison of GO-modified PC and MOC composites, with both prepared and tested under the same conditions. Composites containing up to 1.0 wt% GO were assessed using XRD, SEM, EDS, XRF, MIP, and thermal analysis, as well as mechanical and hygric testing. The results indicate that GO does not change the basic phase structure of either binder system but leads to different responses based on the system. Flexural strength increased by as much as 17.6% in PC and 13.4% in MOC composites. Compressive strength showed an optimal level at moderate GO amounts but declined at higher levels. Water absorption and transport were slightly lower, especially with increased GO amounts. In MOC composites, water resistance improved, shown by higher softening coefficients and retained compressive strength. Thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity increased with more GO content. These findings show that GO's effect varies with the type of binder. In hydration-based PC systems, its impact mainly appears in microstructure and mechanical response. In crystallization-based MOC systems, changes in water performance are more noticeable. The study offers a controlled comparison that aids in designing GO-modified cement-based materials for specific engineering uses.

1. Introduction

Cementitious materials are fundamental to modern construction, offering the structural backbone for everything from buildings to infrastructure. Among them, Portland cement (PC) remains the most widely used binder thanks to its reliable performance, widespread availability, and low cost. However, its production is highly energy-intensive and contributes to nearly 8% of global CO₂ emissions [1]. Beyond the environmental cost, PC-based materials also face technical challenges such as shrinkage, cracking, and poor resistance to water and chemicals, all of which compromise long-term durability. To overcome these drawbacks, alternative binders like magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) have been explored. MOC offers several advantages, including rapid setting, high early strength, and a significantly smaller carbon footprint [2]. Yet despite these benefits, its practical use remains limited due to poor water resistance and concerns about long-term

stability [3]. These limitations have driven growing interest in material innovations that can improve the performance of both PC and MOC. Among the most promising approaches is the incorporation of graphene oxide (GO) as a nano-reinforcement [4–7].

In recent years, a substantial body of research has focused on using GO to enhance the properties of cementitious composites [8–11]. Owing to its large specific surface area, outstanding mechanical strength, and rich surface chemistry, GO can significantly improve the strength, durability, and water resistance of cement-based materials [12,13]. While its effects on Portland cement have been well-studied, the role of GO in MOC systems is still emerging [14,15]. Since the two binders differ in their chemical composition and hydration mechanisms, it is reasonable to expect that the response of the systems to GO addition may differ. Numerous studies have demonstrated that GO can enhance the mechanical strength of PC-based materials [11,16,17]. Research indicates that GO additions in the range of 0.03–0.10 wt% can increase

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compressive strength by 9–15% and flexural strength by 20–30%, primarily due to its ability to bridge cracks, promote hydration, and refine pore structures [17–20]. The crack-bridging mechanism of GO is particularly crucial, as it delays crack propagation by reinforcing the interfacial transition zone between aggregates and the cement matrix [21,22]. Furthermore, the oxygen-containing functional groups on GO interact with hydration products, forming denser and more homogeneous cementitious phases [23–25]. This leads to a refined pore network, reducing permeability and enhancing resistance to water, chloride ions, and sulfate attack [26–31]. The hygric properties of GO-enhanced PC composites are particularly noteworthy. Studies have shown that GO can reduce water absorption and permeability by refining the pore network and blocking capillary pathways [17,23,24,32]. This is crucial for preventing corrosion of embedded steel reinforcement and prolonging the service life of concrete structures [23,30,32].

While MOC exhibits excellent early mechanical strength, it is highly susceptible to water-induced deterioration, which limits its broader application. Recent studies have demonstrated that GO can significantly mitigate MOC's water sensitivity, thereby improving its long-term stability [33]. The addition of 0.1–0.2 wt% GO has been shown to reduce capillary absorption by 24–28% and lower total water absorption by 25–39% [34]. This effect is attributed to the ability of GO to interact with and partially chemically bond to hydration products, leading to a denser and more water-resistant microstructure [23,30,32]. Additionally, GO appears to act as a moisture barrier, slowing down water penetration and minimizing the dissolution of $MgCl_2$ – a common cause of MOC degradation [35]. In terms of mechanical performance, GO has proven highly effective in enhancing MOC's flexural strength and toughness [33]. Unlike traditional Portland cement, MOC has an inherently brittle nature, which limits its ability to withstand tensile stresses [36]. However, research has shown that incorporating 0.1–0.2% GO can increase flexural strength by up to 92%, nearly doubling the material's ability to resist cracking [14]. This remarkable improvement is commonly attributed to the nano-bridging effect, where GO sheets act as reinforcements that link the MOC crystalline phases, preventing crack propagation [9,11,37,38]. Despite these benefits, the exact mechanisms by which GO improves PC and MOC are still being investigated [39,40]. Because PC hardens through hydration while MOC sets via a salt-based crystallization process, the way GO interacts with each system is fundamentally different. In PC, GO enhances hydration, densifies the matrix, and bridges cracks, while in MOC, it primarily improves water resistance and stabilizes the structure. Gaining a deeper understanding of these distinct mechanisms is essential for designing optimized, GO-enhanced cementitious materials. Beyond improving performance, using GO in both traditional and alternative binders may help meet sustainability goals. It can boost durability and possibly extend service life. This can lower material use and reduce emissions over time.

Despite the large amount of research on GO-modified PC composites and the increasing studies on GO integration in MOC, there is still no direct and consistent comparison between these two binder systems. Most published studies look at PC and MOC separately. They often use different mix designs, curing practices, dispersion methods, and testing procedures. Because of this, the reported effects of GO cannot be directly compared. The role of binder chemistry in influencing GO-matrix interactions is not well understood.

In this study, we present a parallel experimental design where graphene oxide is added to Portland cement and magnesium oxychloride cement under the same conditions. By keeping the specimen shape, aggregate size, testing methods, and characterization techniques the same, we can evaluate the effect of GO based on the binder chemistry, not on differences in the experiment. This method allows us to directly assess how hydration-driven (PC) and crystallization-driven (MOC) binding processes affect the reinforcing effectiveness of GO. A comprehensive suite of analytical techniques was employed, including XRD, SEM, EDS, and XRF for phase and elemental analysis; macrostructural

and microstructural characterization, including pore size distribution; and performance evaluation via mechanical testing, water absorption measurements, and thermal analysis.

The objectives of this study are: (1) to systematically evaluate how different amounts of GO affect the mechanical performance of PC- and MOC-based composites; (2) to link mechanical behaviour with microstructural features, pore structure, and phase composition; (3) to assess how graphene oxide impacts hygric and thermal properties that are important for durability; and (4) to clarify the similarities and differences in the main reinforcement mechanisms of GO in hydration-based and crystallization-based cement systems. The findings contribute to the development of high-performance, nano-engineered cements and support sustainable construction through improved durability and material longevity.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

Portland cement (PC) mortars were prepared using CEM I 42.5 R (Heidelberg Materials CZ, Czech Republic), silica sand (Filtrační písky, s. r.o., Czech Republic), and tap water. The cement complies with the EN 197–1 standard [41]. Specific density of PC used was $3.130 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, LOI 3.2 wt%, and Blaine fineness $382 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. The used silica sand was a mixture of three size fractions PG1, PG2, and PG3, with particle sizes of 0–0.5 mm, 0.5–1.0 mm, and 1.0–2.0 mm, respectively. The water-to-cement (w/c) ratio was 0.5.

For the preparation of magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC)-based samples, the following materials were used: MgO (Penta s.r.o., Czech Republic), analytical grade $MgCl_2\cdot 6H_2O$ (Lach-ner, s.r.o., Czech Republic), silica sand (Filtrační písky, s.r.o., Czech Republic) in the three previously mentioned size fractions, and tap water. The MgO powder had a specific density of $3.266 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and a loss on ignition (LOI) of max. 5.0 wt%.

As a nanoadditive for PC and MOC, commercially purchased industrial grade graphene oxide (GO) from ACS Material, LLC, USA, with particle size of 0.2 – 10 μm , was used.

The compositions of the prepared samples are presented in Table 1 and Table 2. The mixtures labelled PC-GO-R and MOC-GO-R serve as reference samples without the addition of GO. Samples containing GO are designated as PC-GO-X and MOC-GO-X, where X represents the concentration of the nanomaterial in weight percent (wt%) relative to the weight of the respective binder. The upper GO dosage of 1.0 wt% was intentionally included to evaluate the effect of overdosage and dispersion-related limitations allowing direct comparison of system sensitivity in PC and MOC matrices. Prepared and cured cement beams are shown in Fig. 1.

For the PC samples, GO was dispersed in the mixing water using a high-shear rotor–stator homogenizer (Ultra Turrax, 10 000 rpm, 5 min). No additional surfactants or chemical dispersing agents were used in order to avoid potential interference with the hydration and crystallization processes of the cementitious matrices. Although ultrasonication and quantitative dispersion characterization methods further improve and assess GO dispersion, they were not applied in the present study. The chosen dispersion procedure was selected to reflect a simple and practically applicable approach commonly reported in the literature for

Table 1
Composition of prepared PC-based samples (g).

Sample	PC	H ₂ O	Sand	GO
PC-GO-R	500	250	3 × 500	-
PC-GO-0.05	500	250	3 × 500	0.38
PC-GO-0.1	500	250	3 × 500	0.75
PC-GO-0.5	500	250	3 × 500	3.75
PC-GO-1.0	500	250	3 × 500	7.50

Table 2
Composition of prepared MOC-based samples (g).

Sample	MgO	MgCl ₂ ·6 H ₂ O	H ₂ O	Sand	GO
MOC-GO-R	500	504.42	312.88	3 × 500	-
MOC-GO-0.05	500	504.42	312.88	3 × 500	0.66
MOC-GO-0.1	500	504.42	312.88	3 × 500	1.32
MOC-GO-0.5	500	504.42	312.88	3 × 500	6.59
MOC-GO-1.0	500	504.42	312.88	3 × 500	13.17

cement-based systems. The limitations associated with GO dispersion, particularly at higher dosages, are therefore considered in the interpretation of the mechanical and microstructural results. This suspension was mixed with PC powder in a planetary mortar mixer (ELE, United Kingdom). After an initial 30 s of mixing, silica sand was added, followed by an additional 60 s of mechanical mixing, brief manual homogenization, and a final 3-minute mixing phase. The fresh PC mortars were poured into molds measuring 40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm, demolded after 24 h, and cured for 27 days in a climatic chamber maintained at (23 ± 2) °C and (90 ± 5)% relative humidity. The curing conditions were selected to ensure sufficient moisture availability for continued hydration and to reflect commonly adopted laboratory curing practices for hydraulic cement-based materials. For each composition, six specimens were prepared; three were used for mechanical testing and the remaining specimens were utilized for complementary analyses.

For the MOC samples, MgCl₂·6 H₂O was first dissolved in tap water to form an aqueous solution. GO was then dispersed in this solution using the same Ultra Turrax settings. The resulting dispersion was combined with MgO powder in the planetary mortar mixer, following the same mixing protocol as used for the PC batch. Silica sand was incorporated after 30 s, followed by further mechanical and manual mixing. The fresh mortar was cast into molds of identical dimensions, demolded after 24 h, and cured for 27 days in a climatic chamber maintained at (23 ± 2) °C and (50 ± 5)% relative humidity. In contrast to hydraulic binders, MOC is a crystallization-based system that does not require external moisture for strength development. Since MOC is sensitive to prolonged exposure to high humidity, curing was performed under controlled laboratory conditions to allow proper phase formation while minimizing moisture-induced instability. Currently, no harmonized European standard specifies curing conditions for MOC-based composites. For each composition, six specimens were prepared; three were used for mechanical testing and the remaining specimens were utilized for complementary analyses.

2.2. Analytical and testing techniques

The particle size distribution of MgO and Portland cement was determined using laser diffraction (LD) with a Mastersizer 3000 device (Malvern Panalytical, UK) equipped with a 4 mW He-Ne laser

(632.8 nm) and a 10 mW LED light source, whereas the granulometry of silica sand was obtained via standard sieve analysis. The chemical composition of both binders and the aggregate was assessed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) with an Axios wavelength-dispersive spectrometer (PANalytical, Netherlands). GO was characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM; EFTEM JEOL 2200 FS, JEOL, Japan) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to examine its morphology and structural features. For TEM analysis, a GO suspension in isopropyl alcohol (1 mg·mL⁻¹) was prepared using ultrasonic probe dispersion. A drop of the suspension was then deposited onto a copper grid and allowed to dry prior to measurement.

The phase composition of the cured samples was analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a Bruker D2 Phaser diffractometer (Bruker AXS, Germany) operating with Cu K α radiation (30 kV, 10 mA), a step size of 0.02025° (2 θ), and a scanning range of 5–80° (2 θ), while their bulk chemical composition was evaluated by XRF for consistency. The microstructural characteristics of the hardened composites were investigated directly on raw fracture surfaces without any additional polishing or resin embedding. Optical microscopy (OM; Navitar macro-optics, USA) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Tescan Lyra, Tescan, Czech Republic) were performed on these fracture surfaces using a 10 kV accelerating voltage. Mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP; Pascal 140 and 440, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was used to assess pore structure. Elemental distribution on fracture surfaces was examined by energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) coupled with SEM using an X-MaxN detector (Oxford Instruments, UK).

Mechanical performance was assessed through compressive and flexural strength testing in accordance with EN 1015–11 using a Heckert PF 100 testing machine (Germany), along with evaluation of the dynamic Young's modulus by ultrasonic pulse velocity measurements. Hygric behavior was characterized by determining 24-hour water absorption and the water absorption coefficient. Thermal transport and storage properties were evaluated using a non-stationary heat pulse apparatus operating on the hot disk principle. For composites based on magnesium oxychloride cement, water resistance was further evaluated by determining the softening coefficient [42]. An overview of the experimental workflow applied in this study is provided in Fig. 2.

For microscopic and phase analyses, different sample preparation methods were used based on the characterization technique. SEM and optical microscopy observations were conducted on fresh fracture surfaces of hardened specimens after 28 days of curing. Before SEM analysis, the fracture surfaces were coated with a thin layer of gold to ensure electrical conductivity. All measurements took place under high-vacuum conditions. EDS analysis was performed on the same SEM specimens under the same experimental conditions. XRD and XRF measurements were carried out on powdered samples made from crushed composites. TEM analysis was used only for GO characterization and did not apply it to the hardened cementitious composites.

Fig. 1. Cured samples prepared for testing.

Fig. 2. Outline of research methodology.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of raw materials

The chemical composition of PC, MgO, and silica sand is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4 presents the particle size distribution of MgO and PC. The dashed lines represent the cumulative particle size curves, while the solid lines show the distribution curves. Up to approximately 10 μm, the MgO powder was finer compared to PC. The particle size distribution parameters d₁₀, d₅₀, and d₉₀ for MgO were 0.8 μm, 3.1 μm, and 53.7 μm, respectively, whereas for PC, the corresponding values were 21.9 μm, 36.1 μm, and 59.1 μm.

The grain size curve of silica sand obtained by sieve analysis is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6 presents the morphology and microstructure of GO as observed by SEM and TEM. The SEM image reveals a crumpled, paper-like morphology characteristic of GO sheets, which tend to wrinkle and

fold due to their ultrathin, flexible nature. This three-dimensional structure is commonly observed in GO materials dried from suspension. The TEM image provides insight into the internal structure of the GO, displaying semi-transparent, overlapping layers with varying contrast, indicative of thickness variations and sheet stacking. Wrinkles, folds, and edge features are also apparent, reflecting the intrinsic flexibility and defect-rich nature of GO. These complementary imaging techniques confirm the presence of highly wrinkled and layered GO sheets.

3.2. Analysis of composites

The cement beams were fractured, and their fracture surfaces were examined by OM (Fig. 7). In both PC and MOC composites, silica sand particles were found to be uniformly distributed within the matrix. Although the oxygen-containing functional groups on GO are expected to improve its dispersibility, GO was still primarily observed in the form of agglomerates in the MOC samples – small black dots were visible. It

Fig. 3. Chemical composition of used raw materials (in wt%).

Fig. 4. Binders' particle size distribution.

should be noted that the dispersion quality of GO is expected to decrease with increasing dosage, which may contribute to the formation of agglomerates observed at higher GO contents and to the corresponding trends in mechanical performance. Nevertheless, with increasing GO

content, these agglomerates became less apparent, likely due to the progressive pigmentation of the matrix. In the PC-based composites, the GO agglomerates were also difficult to discern, most likely because of the naturally grey coloration of the PC matrix.

Elemental analysis of the samples was performed using XRF. The results of the elemental compositions are provided in the [Supporting Information \(SI Table 1 and 2\)](#). As expected, the PC sample set primarily consisted of calcium, silicon, and carbon and light elements that XRF is unable to detect. The Si content gradually increases while Ca content decreases. This change is greater than what we would expect from LOI differences due to adding GO. It is linked not only to how XRF normalizes the data but also to the mixed nature of the composite and how we prepared the samples. Specifically, adding GO may affect the microstructure and fragmentation of the cement matrix and aggregate during sample crushing. This change can lead to a slightly higher representation of Si-rich fractions in the analysed material. However, this does not suggest a change in hydration chemistry. Similarly, the MOC sample set was mainly composed of carbon and light elements, magnesium, silicon, and chlorine. The only detected impurity was iron, most likely introduced from the milling bowl. Since the elemental composition of the samples showed no substantial variation with increasing GO content, [Fig. 8](#) presents the data in the form of pie charts for better clarity.

The XRD patterns, presented in [Fig. 9](#), demonstrate that the phase composition of the PC sample set remains stable with increasing GO

Fig. 5. Grain size of silica sand.

Fig. 6. SEM (left) and TEM (right) micrographs of GO.

Fig. 7. Micrographs of PC-GO-X (left) and MOC-GO-X (right) obtained from OM.

content. All PC samples consistently exhibit crystalline phases corresponding to ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12}\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$), quartz (SiO_2), portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), calcite (CaCO_3), alite (Ca_3SiO_5), and gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Similarly, the MOC sample set shows no substantial variation in phase assemblage upon GO incorporation, with quartz (SiO_2) and MOC phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$) identified as the predominant phases. No additional crystalline phases related to GO addition were observed in either system. These results show that adding GO does not cause noticeable changes in crystalline hydration or crystallization products within the sensitivity limits of the XRD method. It is important to note that because of the low GO content and the composite nature of the samples, XRD mainly detects crystalline phases and cannot identify subtle changes in poorly crystalline or amorphous hydration products. The absence of new crystalline phases suggests that GO does not directly participate in the formation of detectable hydration or crystallization products within either system.

The SEM micrographs of the PC sample set (Fig. 10, left) revealed a heterogeneous microstructure composed of distinct cement hydration products. A dense cementitious matrix was observed, interspersed with needle-like and plate-like formations consistent with typical cement hydration products such as ettringite and portlandite. Due to the resolution limits of SEM and the complex cementitious matrix, GO sheets were not directly visualized at the nanoscale. While SEM observations do not reveal pronounced microstructural differences between the reference and GO-modified samples, changes in particle packing and overall porosity are suggested by the MIP results (Fig. 11). Additionally, the presence of voids and microcracks was evident in all samples, which may be attributed to shrinkage phenomena or incomplete matrix densification. For each sample, a higher-magnification SEM image was acquired from the area highlighted in the corresponding low-magnification micrograph to illustrate local microstructural details.

The SEM micrographs of the MOC sample set (Fig. 10, right) revealed a well-developed crystalline microstructure, characterized predominantly by large, plate-like or needle-like formations associated with phase 5, the principal hydration product of MOC. The matrix appeared densely packed; however, the spatial distribution of GO within the crystalline structure cannot be directly resolved from SEM observations. No pronounced differences in overall matrix density are directly observable from SEM micrographs. Regions exhibiting finer textures, corresponding to silica sand particles, were also observed.

EDS analysis was conducted on all samples and is provided in the Supporting Information file (Fig. SI 1 and Fig. SI 2). In the PC sample set, the elemental distribution is homogeneous throughout the matrix with minor localized regions with elevated carbon signal in high-GO-content samples. The MOC sample set displays homogenous distribution of all elements, only with localized clustering of carbon (GO), where the extent of aggregation became more evident as the GO content increased.

The macrostructural properties of the 28-day composites, along with their standard deviations, are presented in Table 3. The bulk density and specific density values represent mean measurements obtained from four prisms. In PC-based materials, the incorporation of GO resulted in a slight reduction in bulk density, which corresponds with the observed

increase in total open porosity relative to the control composite (PC-GO-R). However, the differences in macrostructural parameters among the GO-modified composites were generally minimal and mostly fell within the range of standard deviation. The observed increase in open porosity may be attributed to the formation of GO agglomerates, as the effective dispersion of nano-additives remains a well-known challenge in composite material manufacturing. Similarly, in MOC composites, comparable macrostructural performance was observed across the investigated samples, apart from MOC-GO-1.0. In this case as well, the differences between the materials were minor or even negligible, indicating that the addition of GO did not measurably alter the bulk structural characteristics of the MOC matrix.

The microstructure of the composites was characterized by pore size distribution, which was evaluated using MIP. Based on the pore size distribution curves presented in Fig. 11, key microstructural parameters, namely total pore volume and average pore size, were determined. To systematically evaluate the influence of GO dosage on microstructural development, these parameters were analysed in direct relation to the mechanical and hygric performance of both composite systems. The resulting data are presented in Table 4. For both types of composites, the total pore volume showed good correlation with the total open porosity values listed in Table 3.

The mechanical properties of the composites are presented in Fig. 12 and table SI Table 3, which also present also standard deviation of measured data. The mechanical strength of the PC-based composites was notably higher compared to the reference material. An exception was observed for the PC composite with the highest GO concentration, PC-GO-1.0, where the compressive strength was reduced by 8.9%. In this context, lower concentrations of GO appear promising for enhancing mechanical resistance, as improved dispersion of the nanoadditive within the matrix can be achieved at reduced dosages. Specifically, improvements in compressive strength were recorded as 8.3%, 8.2%, and 8.7% for PC-GO-0.05, PC-GO-0.1, and PC-GO-0.5, respectively. In terms of flexural performance, a similar trend was observed. The flexural strength increased by 7.1%, 10.0%, and 12.9% for PC-GO-0.05, PC-GO-0.1, and PC-GO-0.5, respectively. Interestingly, even at the highest GO content, flexural performance continued to improve, with PC-GO-1.0 exhibiting a 17.6% increase in flexural strength compared to the reference. The improvement in mechanical performance at low GO contents is consistent with crack-related reinforcement effects commonly reported for GO, although the present data do not allow identification of a single dominant reinforcement mechanism. Conversely, the higher GO content did not further benefit compressive strength and, in fact, had a slight negative effect, likely due to the aggregation of GO particles forming weak zones within the matrix. It is also anticipated that the reinforcing effect of GO is more pronounced at the microscopic level, while the mechanical parameters presented here reflect the averaged macroscopic behaviour of the composites. The addition of GO had no obvious effect on the stiffness of PC composites, the differences in the Young's modulus varied in the range of standard deviation. Quantitatively, the dynamic Young's modulus values evidence quasi-brittle character of PC composites, which agrees with literature data [43,44].

In MOC composites, the contribution of GO to the overall mechanical

Fig. 8. Elemental composition of PC-GO-R (left) and MOC-GO-R (right) in wt%, light elements – elements with atomic number $Z < 11$.

Fig. 9. Diffractograms from XRD of MOC-GO-X (bottom) and PC-GO-X (top).

strength and stiffness was less pronounced compared to that observed in PC-based materials. However, the incorporation of 0.05 wt% GO into the composite mixture (MOC-GO-0.05) resulted in an enhancement in both compressive strength (by 8.9%) and flexural strength (by 13.4%), while maintaining a comparable Young's modulus relative to the reference sample MOC-GO-R. At higher GO dosages, a decline in mechanical strength was observed; nevertheless, except for MOC-GO-1.0, the mechanical properties remained superior to those of the reference material. The values of Young's modulus remained consistent across all tested MOC composites. Similar to findings in PC-GO systems, the deterioration in the dispersion and packing of GO at elevated concentrations within the MOC matrix led to reduced mechanical performance, thereby diminishing the reinforcing and bridging efficiency of the nanofiller.

In general, MOC composites show high mechanical strength, which is further enhanced by the addition of GO. This makes them suitable not only for structural applications but also for the development of advanced high-strength composites. The reinforced MOC-GO matrix provides a mechanical reserve that allows the incorporation of various industrial byproducts and waste materials. This approach enables the production of sustainable composite materials using additives such as fly ash, slag, recycled construction waste, ceramic or glass residues, and stabilized sludges. GO may improve the cohesion and mechanical performance even when lower-quality fillers are used.

Overall, the different trends observed for compressive and flexural strength suggest that these two mechanical parameters respond differently to GO dosage and dispersion quality. Similar trends have been

reported in previous studies on GO-modified cementitious materials [16, 17], where an optimal GO content was observed and higher dosages led to reduced efficiency due to agglomeration effects.

The mechanical performance of both PC- and MOC-based composites should also be interpreted in direct relation to the observed pore structure evolution, microstructural features, and GO dispersion state. In PC-based composites, the increase in flexural strength (up to 17.6%) occurred despite a slight increase in total open porosity and total pore volume as determined by MIP. This indicates that the strength enhancement cannot be attributed to overall densification of the matrix. Instead, the mechanical improvement is primarily associated with microstructural reinforcement mechanisms. SEM observations revealed a heterogeneous matrix with typical hydration products (C-S-H, portlandite, ettringite), without formation of new crystalline phases in XRD patterns, confirming that GO does not alter the phase assemblage but rather affects the microstructure at the nano- and microscale. Although the total porosity slightly increased, the pore size distribution analysis suggests that the proportion of critical capillary pores contributing to crack initiation did not increase proportionally. The presence of GO sheets, even if partially agglomerated, likely contributed to crack-bridging and crack-deflection mechanisms. These mechanisms are more pronounced under flexural loading, where tensile stresses dominate and crack propagation governs failure. The improvement in flexural strength, even at higher GO dosages, supports the assumption that GO sheets act as stress-transfer bridges across microcracks, increasing fracture energy rather than simply compressive load-bearing capacity. In contrast, compressive strength showed an optimal dosage behaviour.

Fig. 10. SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of PC-GO-X and MOC-GO-X composites (the magnified views are taken directly from the marked regions).

At moderate GO contents (0.05–0.5 wt%), improved stress distribution and crack-arrest effects outweigh the negative impact of slightly increased porosity. However, at 1.0 wt% GO, the formation of agglomerates observed in OM and supported by the discussion on dispersion limitations likely created localized weak zones and stress concentrators. Compressive strength is highly sensitive to such heterogeneities, which explains the slight deterioration at higher GO content despite maintained or increased flexural performance.

In MOC-based composites, the strengthening mechanism differs due to the crystallization-based binding system dominated by phase 5. SEM micrographs revealed a well-developed crystalline network. Unlike in PC composites, MOC-GO systems suggest a partial redistribution of

pores within the 0.8–10 μm range at optimal GO dosage, which are known to be mechanically critical capillary pores. This refinement of the pore structure likely contributed to the observed improvement in both compressive and flexural strength at 0.05 wt% GO. However, at higher GO contents, the increase in average pore diameter and total pore volume in some compositions, combined with visible GO clustering, indicates that dispersion-related effects again dominate over potential nucleation or bridging benefits. Since MOC relies on interlocking crystalline phases rather than a C-S-H gel network, the reinforcing efficiency of GO depends strongly on its ability to be uniformly distributed between growing crystals. Agglomerated GO disrupts this crystallization continuity and reduces load transfer efficiency.

Fig. 11. Pore size distribution in PC and MOC composites: a) cumulative curves, b) distribution curves.

Table 3
Macrostructural parameters of composites.

Composite type	Bulk density ρ_b	Specific density ρ_s	Open porosity φ
	kg·m ⁻³	kg·m ⁻³	%
PC-GO-R	2085 ± 16	2488 ± 3	16.2 ± 0.4
PC-GO-0.05	2062 ± 9	2499 ± 3	17.5 ± 0.4
PC-GO-0.1	2047 ± 22	2503 ± 4	17.8 ± 0.7
PC-GO-0.5	2054 ± 18	2495 ± 4	18.1 ± 0.2
PC-GO-1.0	2033 ± 16	2492 ± 3	17.6 ± 0.6
MOC-GO-R	2046 ± 12	2235 ± 4	8.4 ± 0.3
MOC-GO-0.05	2041 ± 5	2259 ± 2	9.7 ± 0.2
MOC-GO-0.1	2040 ± 10	2259 ± 4	9.7 ± 0.4
MOC-GO-0.5	2035 ± 6	2249 ± 3	9.5 ± 0.3
MOC-GO-1.0	2040 ± 8	2228 ± 3	8.4 ± 0.3

The absence of new crystalline phases in XRD patterns for both systems confirms that GO does not directly participate in hydration or crystallization reactions within the detection limits of the method. Therefore, the strengthening or deterioration mechanisms are primarily physical rather than chemical in nature. GO acts as: (i) a nano-scale crack-bridging reinforcement, (ii) a microstructural modifier influencing pore size distribution, (iii) a potential nucleation surface for hydration products (although not directly confirmed by phase analysis),

Table 4
Microstructural parameters of composites measured by MIP.

Composite type	Total pore volume	Average pore diameter
	cm ³ ·g ⁻¹	μm
PC-GO-R	0.0669	0.0228
PC-GO-0.05	0.0675	0.0249
PC-GO-0.1	0.0731	0.0293
PC-GO-0.5	0.0746	0.0237
PC-GO-1.0	0.0675	0.0277
MOC-GO-R	0.0572	0.0213
MOC-GO-0.05	0.0620	0.0258
MOC-GO-0.1	0.0680	0.0210
MOC-GO-0.5	0.0612	0.0263
MOC-GO-1.0	0.0523	0.0266

(iv) and, at higher dosages, a defect source due to agglomeration.

Overall, the mechanical behaviour of GO-modified composites results from the competition between microstructural refinement and defect formation. At optimal dosages, crack-bridging and pore structure modification dominate, leading to enhanced strength. At excessive dosages, agglomeration-induced heterogeneity and increased local porosity become the governing factors, particularly affecting compressive strength.

A more quantitative comparison between porosity parameters and

Fig. 12. Mechanical parameters of 28-day PC composites and MOC composites.

mechanical performance further clarifies the observed trends. In PC-based composites, the incorporation of 0.05–0.5 wt% GO resulted in an increase in compressive strength of approximately 8–9%, while the total pore volume increased from 0.0669 to

0.0731–0.0746 $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ (Table 4), corresponding to a rise of up to ~11%. Similarly, open porosity increased from 16.2% to approximately 18%. Despite this increase in total porosity, strength was enhanced, indicating that mechanical performance is not governed solely by total

pore volume. This suggests that the distribution and connectivity of pores, rather than their absolute volume, play a dominant role. The MIP data indicate variations in average pore diameter and redistribution among gel and capillary pore ranges, which are mechanically more critical than total porosity alone. Therefore, moderate GO addition improves crack resistance and stress transfer even without global densification of the matrix. In contrast, at 1.0 wt% GO, compressive strength decreased by 8.9% relative to the reference, while total pore volume returned close to the reference level. This indicates that strength deterioration at high GO content is not directly caused by increased total porosity but is more likely related to agglomeration-induced heterogeneity and localized stress concentrations observed in microstructural analysis.

A similar non-linear relationship between porosity and strength was observed in MOC-based composites. At 0.05 wt% GO, compressive strength increased by 8.9%, although total pore volume increased from 0.0572 to 0.0620 cm³ · g⁻¹. The strengthening effect therefore appears to result from microstructural refinement and improved load transfer rather than simple porosity reduction.

In summary, from a quantitative perspective, the results demonstrate that the relationship between GO content, porosity, and strength is non-linear. Mechanical performance is governed by the balance between microstructural reinforcement mechanisms and defect formation associated with GO agglomeration, rather than by total porosity alone.

The results of water absorption measurement are presented in Fig. 13. Both 24 h water absorption by volume (W_{a24h}) and 24 h water absorption by mass (W_{a24m}) are shown. In both categories of composites, the water absorption was slightly reduced by incorporation of GO.

Generally, water ingress and storage are influenced by two main factors: (i) changes in porosity and pore size distribution, and (ii) physicochemical characteristics of the incorporated nanoadditive. Individual GO sheets are intrinsically hydrophilic due to their oxygen-containing functional groups, which interact with water molecules [45,46]. However, in cementitious matrices, GO is partially present in aggregated form due to π - π stacking interactions, van der Waals forces, and dispersion limitations [47,48].

The observed reduction in water uptake cannot be directly correlated with total porosity alone, as several GO-modified composites exhibited slightly increased open porosity compared to the reference samples (Table 3). Instead, the hygric behaviour appears to be governed primarily by redistribution of pore sizes and changes in pore connectivity. MIP results (Fig. 11, Table 4) indicate variations in average pore diameter and redistribution between gel and capillary pore ranges. Since capillary suction and moisture transport are mainly controlled by the

size and continuity of capillary pores, even moderate changes within the critical pore diameter range may influence water uptake kinetics.

Although individual GO sheets are hydrophilic, partial agglomeration at higher dosages may locally alter pore connectivity and structural homogeneity. Rather than assuming a true hydrophobic behaviour of GO clusters, the reduction in water transport at higher GO contents is more consistently attributed to disruption of continuous capillary pathways and increased tortuosity within the pore network.

Gel pores are generally associated with physically adsorbed or bound water and contribute less to continuous capillary transport compared to larger capillary pores. Water molecules confined in gel pores may interact with hydration products such as C-S-H in PC or phase 5 in MOC through hydrogen bonding interactions [49]; however, their contribution to bulk water transport remains limited due to restricted connectivity.

The relative redistribution toward smaller pore ranges in selected compositions is therefore consistent with the measured decrease in water absorption coefficient A_w (kg · m⁻² · s^{-1/2}) shown in Fig. 14. For both PC- and MOC-based composites, differences in water transport behaviour were negligible at GO additions up to 0.1 wt%. At higher GO dosages, a moderate reduction in water transport was observed. This trend is consistent with the pore structure redistribution discussed above and suggests that GO influences moisture transport primarily through modification of capillary connectivity rather than through intrinsic changes in material hydrophobicity.

The durability of MOC composites against water was characterised by softening coefficient Sc (%) and residual compressive strength f_{cr} (MPa) that are shown in Fig. 15. In line with the partially hindered moisture ingress, the use of GO increased both the residual compressive strength and softening coefficient as compared to that of reference composite MOC-GO-R. In addition, the bridging of cracks formed during the decomposition of phase 5 in water by graphene oxide sheets apparently contributed to the enhancement of water resistance of MOC-GO samples. In crack bridging, GO sheets span across cracks and hold the crack faces together, thereby increasing the energy required for crack propagation [22]. The pull-out mechanism, i.e. the interfacial bonding between GO and the matrix, may also contribute to the enhancement of residual compressive strength [16,45]. The effectiveness of the pull-out mechanism depends on the quality of the interfacial interaction between GO and the MOC matrix. The primary binding phase of MOC (phase 5) contains structural hydroxyl groups that may interact with oxygen-containing functional groups on GO (-OH, -COOH,

Fig. 13. 24 h water absorption of hardened composites.

Fig. 14. Water absorption coefficient of hardened composites.

Fig. 15. Softening coefficient and residual compressive strength.

epoxy groups) through hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions. Although no direct spectroscopic evidence of chemical bonding was obtained in this study, such physicochemical interactions, together with mechanical interlocking of GO sheets within the intergrown crystalline network of phase 5, may contribute to enhanced crack resistance and improved water stability.

The dry thermal conductivity λ_d ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) and volumetric heat capacity c_v ($\text{MJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) of the examined composites are presented in Fig. 16. The thermal performance of the composites was influenced primarily by two competing factors: (i) changes in porosity and (ii) the intrinsic thermal conductivity of GO, which depends on its degree of oxidation, structural ordering, and synthesis conditions [51]. In porous cementitious materials, thermal conductivity is largely governed by the volume fraction and connectivity of air-filled pores, which act as thermal insulators. An increase in total open porosity would therefore normally be expected to reduce thermal conductivity. However, in the present study, several GO-modified compositions exhibited slightly increased porosity while thermal conductivity increased simultaneously. This behaviour indicates that the contribution of GO may partially compensate for the porosity-related reduction in heat transport associated with moderate porosity increase. Even at low concentrations, the relatively high intrinsic thermal conductivity of GO sheets may

Fig. 16. Thermal parameters of composites.

contribute to enhanced heat transfer pathways within the solid phase. From the perspective of effective medium behaviour, the incorporation of conductive nano-inclusions may increase overall thermal conductivity provided that partial connectivity within the solid phase is achieved [45]. A similar trend was observed for both PC- and MOC-based composites. In particular, increasing GO dosage in MOC systems resulted in a consistent rise in thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity, suggesting that GO acts as a thermally conductive component within the otherwise less conductive cementitious matrix.

Considering the absence of new crystalline phases in XRD analysis and the observed changes in performance parameters, GO appears to act primarily as a nano-scale microstructural modifier rather than forming new reaction products. Within the limits of the applied analytical techniques, its influence is therefore better attributed to physical interactions and dispersion-related effects than to direct chemical participation in hydration or crystallization reactions. Overall, the results show that the effect of GO depends on the system. In PC composites, it mainly affects microstructural and mechanical responses without changing the phase composition. In MOC composites, it also results in changes in water-related performance. However, this study does not provide a clear identification of the underlying physical or chemical interaction mechanisms.

4. Conclusion

This study compared the effects of GO on PC and MOC under the same experimental conditions. The results demonstrate that the response to GO is binder-dependent under the investigated conditions. It relates to the different binding mechanisms of hydration in PC and crystallization in MOC. In both binders, GO affected pore structure and moisture-related behaviour. Moderate amounts improved flexural strength, while compressive strength showed an optimal dosage range. Higher GO levels reduced effectiveness, likely due to dispersion issues. In MOC composites, GO resulted in a measurable, though moderate, improvement in the water resistance. Although moderate in magnitude, this enhancement is relevant considering the inherent moisture sensitivity of MOC systems. XRD analysis confirmed that GO does not change the basic phase composition of either system. Instead of finding a single dominant reinforcement method, the results reveal binder-specific response patterns. In PC, GO mainly contributes to microstructural refinement and flexural performance. In MOC, it more significantly enhances water resistance and mechanical performance.

The key contribution of this work is the experimental setup, which allows for a direct comparison of binder-specific behaviour. From a sustainability viewpoint, improving durability and optimizing material performance are important for reducing the environmental impact of cement-based materials. Some limitations need recognition. The behaviour of GO in MgCl_2 -based environments was not directly studied, and long-term durability, scalability, and cost were outside the focus of this lab study. Future research should concentrate on dispersion analysis, long-term performance assessment, and dosage optimization to better understand GO–binder interactions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zbyšek Pavlík: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Milena Pavlíková:** Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Adam Pivák:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Martina Záleská:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Michal Lojka:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data

curation. Adéla Jiríčková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

There are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2026.145870](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2026.145870).

Data availability

According to Open Science principles, raw data are available at DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15544218>

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